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**ADEQUACY OF RESOURCES FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF BUSINESS EDUCATION
PROGRAMME IN FEDERAL COLLEGE OF EDUCATION, YOLA**

Hussaina Maryam Barkindo¹, Zara Jika², Babangida Haruna³ & Mahmud Muhammed⁴

^{1,2,3&4}Vocational Education Department, Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University-Yola

08036093757/08144539634, muhammedbashir55@gmail.com

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Abstract

The study assessed the adequacy of instructional resources available for business education programmes in Federal College of Education Yola in Adamawa State, Nigeria, in relation to the standards stipulated by the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE). The study adopted the ex-post facto research design and three research questions guided the study; the population of the study was strictly the business education department of Federal College of Education Yola only, while the data for the study was collected through direct observation using the NCCE benchmarks as inventory and analysed using ratio and percentage scores. The study found that the available lecturers for business education programme in the college are adequate and that, physical facilities available for business education programmes are adequate, and that equipment and supplies in the typing laboratories, shorthand studios and model offices were found to be grossly inadequate in the college. Based on these findings therefore, the researchers recommended among others, that business education departments should be supplied with appropriate and adequate equipment for improve content delivery.

Keywords: Adequacy, lecturers, Resources, equipment, NCCE

Introduction

Education is generally seen as an aggregate of all the processes by which a child or young adult develops his/her abilities, attitudes and other forms of behavior which are of value to the society in which he lives. It is a conscious training of the young people which would be useful to him/her and to the society to which he/she belongs. Education is universally recognized as an instrument for social, political, scientific and technological development. This is the reason why no society can afford to play with the education of its citizens as this could result to a snail speed (Esene, 2012).

Business Education is an aspect of total education programme. Ohiwerei and Azih (2010) describes Business Education as the education for the acquisition and development of skills and competences, attitudes and attributes which are necessary for efficiency of the economic system. It is an intellectual and vocational preparation of people for earning a living in a contemporary industrial and business environment. Business Education encompasses education for office occupations, business teaching, business administration and economic understanding. One can as well agree that Business Education is the instruction given in tertiary institutions to prepare students for jobs in teaching, industries, administration and entrepreneurship. To this end, if general education is thought of as the adjustment of an individual to his environment, then Business Education should simply be seen as a means of adjustment of the individual to his business environment.

College of education is one of the post-secondary educational institutions in Nigeria designed specifically to train and prepare students for the teaching industry. Colleges of education provide exposure and learning for prospective teachers at the level of the Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE). Similarly, apart from the professional and general education courses students of the colleges are also exposed to their chosen subject areas such as office technology, accounting and marketing education. Hence the National Policy on education (2014) section 8(70-72) has provided a place for vocational education programme (Business Education). However, in order to implement and achieve these lofty objectives of business education at colleges of education, the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) which is the government regulatory and supervisory agency for the colleges of education in Nigeria stipulates the minimum standards of course offering and resource inputs that need to be available for the establishment and administration of business education programme at that level. The NCCE (2015) classified resources in business education into the following: Physical Facilities (this includes classrooms, staff offices, libraries, typing laboratories, model offices and shorthand studios), Equipment and Supplies (this includes the computers, photocopiers, tape-recorders, headphones, perforators, punching machines, stopwatch, stapling machine and others), Personnel (this includes the lecturers, instructors, technologists, and other support staff). However, instructional resources are important aspect of these resource inputs.

Instructional resources according to Obioma, Chukwuma, & Ajudeonu (2012) are those basic requirements that aid and facilitate effective school teaching and learning. Instructional resources comprise human beings (teachers), facilities and equipment for teaching and learning. In business education, instructional resources include the business educators (lecturers), typing laboratories, shorthand studios, model offices, facilities such as classroom, library, as well as equipment such as computers, typewriters among others. The importance of office in an organization cannot be overemphasized. In the academic circle, the office is more than a home. It is described as a second home for lecturers because much of their academic time is spent in the office engaging in one form of research, preparing for lecture, attending to students and the likes. The most used of self-instructional facility has been the book. The book is still the most economical, most easily accessible and means of conveying information and ideas, considering the cost, size and operating problems of most instructional media. It is indeed the primary and basic source of information and idea in business education. Bakare (2011) opines that nothing has yet replaced the printed words (book) as the key element in the educational process and as a result, textbooks are central to schooling at all levels. In schools, book collections are found in the library.

The library is a repository and/or reservoir of books, tape, newspapers etc for people to read, study or borrow. The main purpose of library is to make available to students, teachers and researchers at easy convenience, all books, periodicals and other reproduced materials which are of interest and value to them. The importance of library has been demonstrated by the government in the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2014) when it states that every state needs to provide funds for the establishment of libraries in all her educational institutions. Typing Laboratory and shorthand studio are seen conceptualized as rooms or buildings specifically built for teaching by demonstration of theoretical phenomenon into practical terms. Laboratories and studios are essential to the teaching of business education and the success of some of its courses is much dependent on the laboratory/studio and the provisions made for them. The teacher assumes a position of dispenser of knowledge with the laboratory/studio serving the function of drill or verification and at the other extreme, the teacher assumes the position of guide to learning and laboratory/studio as a place where knowledge is discovered.

Aimola (2010) posited that some courses in science and vocational education cannot be considered as complete without including some practical work. The model office is a working prototype of operations which reflects the real

environment of a business office as closely as is practically possible. Business education model office is designed in such a way that it represents the actual operations happening in the real offices of a business situation. It is used to teach office clerical and secretarial practice. The model office is a simulation system which is used to enable business education students to experience working conditions and standards likely to be encountered in the real business offices after school. A business education model office usually has a receptionist, equipped with facilities and gadgets of a modern office.

Lecturers are the key facilitators of business education programme, as they design the curriculum, deliver the instruction, assess the learning outcomes, and mentor the students. However, according to a study by Ajisafe, Omotayo, & Edeh (2014), there is a gap between the demand and supply of lecturers for business education programme in Nigeria, due to factors such as low enrolment, high attrition, poor remuneration, inadequate training, and lack of motivation. The shortage of lecturers affects the quality and effectiveness of business education programme, and compromises the achievement of its objectives and goals. Therefore, there is an urgent need to address this issue and ensure the availability and retention of competent and committed lecturers for business education programme in Nigeria.

The implementation of business education programme in many schools faces a major obstacle among them are lack of adequate equipment. Ajayi (2015) found that the said equipment to include computers, printers, scanners, projectors, internet access, software, and other tools are essential for facilitating effective teaching and learning of business concepts and practices. Without this equipment, students cannot access relevant information, perform practical tasks, develop digital literacy, or engage in collaborative projects. In analyzing the implication of obvious inadequacy of equipment, Ajisafe, Omotayo & Edeh (2014) were of the opinion that it hinders the quality and relevance of business education programme, and limits the potential of students to become competent and confident business professionals. Therefore, there is an urgent need to address this issue and provide sufficient and appropriate equipment for business education programme in schools.

Furthermore, in order to ensure that these minimum standards are maintained, the NCCE conducts a routine accreditation exercise of programmes run in the colleges of education. The major objective of accreditation programme according to National Board for Technical Education (2014) is to ensure that schools attain, sustain and ultimately exceed the minimum standards in curriculum, staffing, physical facilities and equipment. Okolocha and Baba (2016) observed that in colleges of education, a lot of fraud is being perpetrated by management in the effort to meet the accreditation agency's stipulations. In their view, equipment and facilities are often borrowed only to be returned once the accreditation is over leaving the programme not richer after the accreditation visit. This is the situation of many tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

However, instructional resources have been observed as a potent factor to qualitative and quantitative education. The importance to teaching and learning of the provision of instructional resources cannot be over-emphasized. Facilities and equipment constitute a strategic factor in organizational functioning and determine to a very large extent the smooth functioning of any social organization or system including education (Bakare 2011) Similarly, availability and adequacy of instructional resources promote effective teaching and learning activities in schools while their inadequacy and/or unavailability may affect the academic performance of the learner negatively. The success of any system is a function of the available resources to run the system. Business education programme as a system can only be effectively implemented with adequate educational resources. Teaching facilities and equipment help to stimulate the interest of the students. Whenever these facilities and equipment are optimally utilized, they generate greater students' interest in the learning system and also enhance retention of ideas. In view of this, Okwuanaso (2011) maintained that by inference, instructional resources have been positively linked with educational efficiency, students' academic performance and their capabilities when they leave

school. This unwholesome situation of education in Nigeria has subsequently brought a growing concern about the quality and quantity of trained teachers and facilities in our schools. As the public intensifies its criticisms of the education system in Nigeria, experts in education and related field are also intensifying their search for the enhancement of quality education at all levels.

Hence, this study assessed the quality of available content and resources available for business education programme at the Federal College of Education in Adamawa State of Nigeria in relation to NCCE standards. The assessment of the resources would be based on the minimum standards stipulated by NCCE (2012) as its benchmark.

Statement of the Problem

Nowadays business education graduates are unable to fit into the world of work and are found roaming about the street jobless. Could it be the half-baked nature of Business Education graduates i.e. incompetence of Business Education graduates, which could be traceable to their inability to fit into the world of work. Could it be as a result of obsolete facilities, incompetent lecturers or inadequate structures and resources?

On the other hand, the number of students appears to have out-paced the available resources. To this end, the need to match the growing students' enrolment with a corresponding increase in the provision of relevant and modern learning resources cannot be under estimated. However, it is particularly worrisome to note that Nigerian tertiary institutions seem to be fast declining, especially in the area of resources required for the educational production processes. A careful look at the nation's schools may show that they are struggling with limited resources and non-functional facilities. This of course, may have a consequent effect on the products of these institutions. Hence, the need to assess the quality of content and resources available for business education programme at the Federal College of Education in Adamawa State of Nigeria in relation to NCCE minimum standards

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to determine the adequacy of educational resources in teaching and learning Business Education in Federal College of Education, Yola Adamawa State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

1. Determine the adequacy of available lecturers for business education programme in the Federal College of Education Yola Adamawa State in relation to NCCE standards.
2. Determine the adequacy of physical facilities available for business education programme in the Federal College of Education Yola Adamawa State in relation to NCCE standards.
3. Ascertain the adequacy of equipment and supply for the implementation of Business Education in the Federal College of Education, Yola base on NCCE minimum standard?

Research Questions

The following research questions were drawn in the course of the study;

1. How adequate are the available lecturers for Business Education in the Federal College of Education, Yola, based on NCCE minimum bench mark?
2. How adequate are the physical facilities for Business Education in the Federal College of Education, Yola, based on NCCE minimum standard?
3. How adequate are the equipment and supply for the implementation of Business Education in the Federal College of Education, Yola, based on NCCE minimum standard?

Methodology

The design adopted for the study is ex-post facto design. Akuezuilo and Agu (20103) describe ex-post facto design as a design that seeks to find out the factors or conditions associated with certain occurrence, outcomes, situation or process by analysing past events or of already existing conditions. The study was carried out in Yola, the capital city of Adamawa state and specifically in the department of business education of the Federal College of Education Yola.

The population of this study is confined to business education departments of Federal College of Education Yola. Akuezuilo and Agu (2013) maintained that population in research and statistics is used in a more specialized sense to include not just people, but also institutions, events, animals, objects, departments and things who or which have common characteristics.

The instrument for this study was the NCCE Benchmark inventory for instructional resources with regards to business education programmes. The NCCE Benchmark inventory is a standard checklist of resources required for business education programmes at the colleges of education in Nigeria. The checklist (instrument) is already validated and standardized by NCCE, hence, there was no validation of the instrument again. The checklist was completed through a direct observation conducted by the researchers in the six business education departments of the colleges of education.

In order to answer the research questions, the data collected was analysed using ratio analysis and percentage score. The benchmark for the analysis is the specifications by NCCE (2015) and the appropriate remarks are adequate and not adequate. Resources were regarded as adequate if the percentage available is 100 and above, while not adequate if the percentage available is less than 100.

Results

Research Question One: How adequate are the available lecturers for the implementation of business education programme in Federal College of Education in Adamawa State?

Table 1. Adequacy of lecturers for business education programme

NCCE Benchmark	Students' Population	Expected Number of Lecturer relation to Benchmark	Surplus/ Deficiency	% Available	Remark
1:30	406	13	9	169%	A

NA=Not Adequate, A=Adequate, *=Deficiency

The results presented in table 1 show that the lecturers available for Business Education Programme in Federal College of Education Yola are adequate in relation to NCCE minimum benchmark. The percentages of lecturers available in relation to the minimum benchmark is 169%. The percentage is greater than 100; hence the number of lecturers for business education is adequate.

Research Question Two: How adequate are the physical facilities available for business education programme in Federal College of Education Yola in relation to NCCE minimum standards?

Table 2. Adequacy of physical facilities for business education programme

S/n	Physical Facilities	FCE YOLA	Remark
1. Classroom (Chairs/desk)			
	Benchmark (seat)	30:30	
	Number Available	4(800)	
	% Available	114%	Adequate
2. Typing Lab			
	Benchmark	1	
	Number Available	2	
	% Available	200%	Adequate
3. Shorthand Studio			
	Benchmark	1	
	Number Available	1	
	% Available	100%	Adequate
4. Model Office			
	Benchmark	1	
	Number Available	1	
	% Available	100%	Adequate
5. Bus. Edu. Library			
	Benchmark (Books)	1:10	
	Number Available	273	
	% Available	4%	Not adequate
6. Lecturer’s Office			
	Benchmark	1:1	
	Number Available	12	
	% Available	60%	Not adequate
7. ICT Lab.			
	Benchmark	1	
	Number Available	0	
	% Available	0%	Not adequate

S/N 5:1:10 = student to ten books, S/N 6: 1:1 = one Lecturer to one office

The result in table 2 shows that the available classroom capacities for business education departments in Federal Colleges of Education Yola are adequate. The school scored above 100% for available seating capacity. The benchmark for classroom seat is typically thirty chairs/desk for thirty students. Also, the table reveals that the business education department have typing laboratories and one each for shorthand studio and model office. This is considered adequate as stipulated by NCCE standards, but ICT Laboratory is not available in the department.

Research Question Three: How adequate are the equipment and supplies for the implementation of Business Education in the Federal College of Education, Yola, based on NCCE minimum standard?

Table 3. Adequacy of equipment and supplies in the typing laboratories

S/N	Equipment/ Supplies	FCE YOLA	Remark
1.	Typewriters		
	Benchmark	30:30	
	Number Available	175	
	% Available	25%	Not Adequate
2.	Computer/Laptops		
	Benchmark	1:3	
	Number Available	35	
	% Available	15%	Not Adequate
3.	Typing chairs		
	Benchmark	30:30	
	Number Available	210	
	% Available	30%	Not Adequate
4.	Typewriter & Computer		
	Benchmark	30:30	
	Number Available	210	
	% Available	30%	Not Adequate
5.	Instructor's Table		
	Benchmark	1:30	
	Number Available	4	
	% Available	17%	Not Adequate
6.	Instructor's chairs		
	Benchmark	1:30	
	Number Available	4	
	% Available	17%	Not Adequate
7.	Wastepaper Bin		
	Benchmark	4:30	
	Number Available	6	
	% Available	6%	Not adequate
8.	Stapling removers		
	Benchmark	4:30	
	Number Available	2	
	% Available	2%	Not Adequate
9.	Perforator		
	Benchmark	2:30	
	Number Available	0	
	% Available	0%	Not Adequate
10.	Stopwatch		
	Benchmark	2:30	

Number Available	3	Not Adequate
% Available	6%	Not Adequate
11. Wall Clock		
Benchmark	1:30	
Number Available	2	
% Available	9%	Not Adequate
12. Demonstration stand		
Benchmark	1:30	
Number Available	2	
% Available	9%	Not Adequate
13. English dictionary		
Benchmark	1:30	
Number Available	2	
% Available	9%	Not Adequate
14. Filing Cabinet		
Benchmark	2:30	
Number Available	3	
% Available	6%	Not Adequate

The results in table 3 above shows that all the equipment and supplies in the laboratories in business education department of Federal College of Education Yola are not adequate in relation to the NCCE minimum standards. This is reflected in the percentages scored by all the items (below 100%) in the departments as such, one can generally interpret that, the equipment and supplies in the laboratories of the business education department of FCE Yola are inadequate.

Summary of Major Findings

The following are the summary of the major findings of the study:

1. Available lecturers for business education programme in Federal College of Education Yola Adamawa State are adequate.
2. The physical facilities available for the implementation of business education programme in Federal College of Education Yola, Adamawa State is adequate as set by NCCE minimum standards
3. The equipment and supplies for the implementation of business education programme in Federal College of Education Yola, Adamawa State is inadequate as set by NCCE minimum standards

Discussion of Findings

The examination of research question one's findings reveals that the number of lecturers available for the business education program at FCE Yola is sufficient. This finding somewhat is contrary to an earlier position maintained by Ajisafe, Omotayo & Edeh (2014) who claimed that business education programs at Nigerian tertiary institutions lacked sufficient technical staff and lecturers. In a related study, Chukwunwendu (2015) found that there aren't enough business education teachers in our schools. However, as can be seen in the later portion of this study, a number studies are bringing to notice the realization of the necessity for adequate lecturers. Therefore, every college of education should make an attempt to go above and above the minimum standards for lecturers.

In research question two, the result of the analysis reveals that physical facilities (classrooms, typing laboratories, shorthand studios and model offices) for business education programmes of FCE Yola are adequate. By implication, this finding shows that physical facilities such as the classrooms (chairs/desk), typing laboratories, shorthand studios and model offices are available and adequate as required. This finding did not agree with the submission of Esene (2012) that business education as a department in Nigerian schools is struggling with many challenges such as limited office accommodation for staff. The importance of offices especially in the academic circle cannot be overemphasized.

The analysis of research question three indicates that the equipment and supplies in the typing laboratories of business education department in FCE Yola are generally not adequate. This finding conforms to the previous study of Ajayi (2015) who found that the typing pools of secondary schools only exist in vacuum and most at times with non-functional typewriters and computers. Similarly, Ajisafe, Omotayo & Edeh, (2014) observed that the supply of typewriters and computers to business education departments is limited considering the increase in students' enrolment. The computers, typewriters and other equipment in the laboratories of business education are far below standard. This is not good for a skill subject/course like business education.

Conclusion

The achievement of business education objectives requires instructional resources (both human and material). However, this study's mixed findings on the adequacy of resources lead to the conclusion that more needs to be filled in order to adequately resource the business education program for better service delivery. Therefore, every stakeholder should work to guarantee that the business education program and its deliverables are of high quality, and that the NCCE minimum requirements are adhered to. This includes providing enough lecturers, facilities, and equipment.

Recommendation

In the light of the above findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Management of colleges of education shall encourage the improvement of the quality and adequacy of teaching staff particularly in business education.
2. Proactive maintenance culture should be put in place to continuously work towards updating existing physical facilities for sustainability of the programme.
3. Shortages of equipment and supplies should be made adequate to ensure proper implementation of the business education programme.

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